

ISic3454

I.Sicily inscription 3454

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.10.30 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

Mineo

Provenance

Territory of Mineo, probably contrada Favarotta (37.307741,
14.710805)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Mineo, Museo Civico Corrado
Tamburino Merlini, inventory 5199

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 491431

EDCS 55702037

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2009.0439

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Rizzone, V.G. 2009. Iscrizioni tardoantiche da Mineo (CT). *Epigraphica*. 71: 426-437. At 431-434 no.2 fig.3

Cordano, F. 2014. Materiale vecchio e nuovo dalla Sicilia orientale. In Alfieri Tonini, T., Struffolino, S.(eds.), *Dinamiche culturali ed etniche nella Sicilia orientale dall'età classica all'epoca ellenistica*. Trento. pp. 105-111. At 109 no.11

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